

D5.3: Results Interpretation

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
CBA	Cost Benefit Analysis
CBR	Cost Benefit Ratio
CE	Circular Economy
EoL	End-of-Life
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FU	Functional unit
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP100	Global Warming Potential
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
R1	Round 1 of implementation
R2	Round 2 of implementation
R3	Round 3 of implementation
SB	System boundaries
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive interpretation of the findings from the Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), the Systemic Innovation Readiness Levels (SIRL) and the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). The analysis is conducted from a grouped perspective, with groups defined based on factors such as clusters, geographical location, context, key actors, and gender perspective.

For each group, various impacts—economic, environmental, and social—are systematically evaluated. This approach allows for a more detailed examination of how sustainability initiatives and their outcomes differ across various settings.

By adopting this grouped perspective, it becomes possible to identify not only overarching trends but also specific, context-dependent effects that might otherwise be overlooked. This method ensures a more nuanced and equitable understanding of the effectiveness of sustainability measures across diverse groups and environments.

1 Introduction

1.0 ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables.

Impact assessment is important for evaluating project performance and achieving goals. To address this, 3 distinct deliverable focus on assessing impacts: D5.2 concentrates on the impacts of each SILL, D5.3 provides analysis by grouping, and D11.4 examines impacts at the overall project level, as illustrated in the figures below.

Figure 3: The different foci of 3 deliverables dealing with impacts

Figure 4: Each deliverable has a unique focus of its analysis

WP 5 is structured around three core tasks—5.1, 5.2, and 5.3—each corresponding to a key deliverable.

In Task 5.1, DIGI and its partners will refine ZeroW's impact assessment methodology, tailoring it to the specific needs of each SILL. This methodology will focus on three main aspects: tracking the progress of SILL innovations using SIRLs, assessing the environmental, economic, and social impacts through LCSA, and ensuring fairness in the distribution of benefits through a 'just transition' approach. Additionally, a digital tool will be developed to allow all project partners to access and utilize this assessment, building on the European Platform on LCA. The outcomes of Task 5.1 are captured in Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1).

In Task 5.2, led by ITC, the methodology developed in Task 5.1 will be applied to assess the sustainability impacts of innovations demonstrated in each SILL. This task will evaluate the effects on local economies and employment, while identifying risks, sustainability trade-offs, and ensuring equitable distribution of impacts among different actors. Special attention will be given to regions facing socio-economic challenges due to the transition towards climate neutrality, with a focus on development, reskilling, and environmental rehabilitation. The findings from this task are detailed in Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2).

Task 5.3, led by DIGI, will interpret the results from Task 5.2, providing insights from cluster, regional, contextual, actor, and gender-based perspectives. These findings will be compiled into a 'lessons learnt' report, which will guide future actions and help identify European regions where ZeroW's SILL innovations could be effectively scaled. This task is documented in the current deliverable, D5.3.

The connection between D5.2 and D5.3 lies in how SILL performance is evaluated and interpreted. In D5.2, the sustainability of each SILL is assessed using LCSA and CBA methodologies. These results are then used in D5.3 to compare actual reductions in FLW with the targets outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA).

The Strategic Plan is a key reference in D5.3, offering insights into the planned reductions and verifying if SILL activities are on track. It also provides a broader understanding of each SILL's strategy for reducing FLW.

Furthermore, D5.3 will serve as input for and for D6.3, which develops regional scaling strategies. The context-based interpretation provided by D5.3 ensures that local conditions are taken into account in these scaling efforts.

1.1 Mapping ZeroW outputs

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D5.3 Results interpretation	Results interpretations – Will provide cluster-, place-, context-, actor & gender-based interpretation of results, R, PU, Internal version 1 M26, Internal version 2 M32, Final version M48.		<p>The results of the assesment are obtained by the LCSA and CBA explained in D5.2.</p> <p>This deliverable interpret those results based on cluster-, place-, context-, actor and gender and provides lessons learnt for the SILLs of how to improve their demonstrators in the remaining rounds.</p>
TASKS			
T5.3 Cluster-, place-, context- & actor-based consolidation &	T5.3 will interpret the results of T5.2 from the:	Introduction	<p>This chapter provides the summary of the main findings of the assessments done in T5.2 and described in D5.2 to provide context and background for the further analysis in the current document that is based on those assessments.</p>

interpretation of results

cluster-,

Cluster-based
interpretation
results

This chapter provides the interpretation of the assessments from the perspectives of the four clusters related to the food supply chain the ZeroW innovations are grouped into:

- Post harvest
- Food processing
- Retail
- Consumers

place-,

Place-based
interpretation
results

This chapter provide analysis of the assessments in relation to the geographical areas where the innovations have been implemented. It also provides the characteristics of those areas where this is relevant to the scaling up of the solutions.

context-,

Context-based interpretation results

This chapter provides additional context of related to the socio-economic aspects affecting the innovations, such as interest in FLW, experience of the relevant actor in the specific area of innovation, identified barriers affecting the implementation of the innovations and the environmental specifics.

actor-

Actor-based interpretation results

In this chapter the assessment of the innovations is analysed through the perspective of the food supply chain actors, as well as the ones that are contributing to the reduction of the FLW through the innovations, such as foodbanks, packing industry, alternative protein producers, etc. stakeholders as identified by the SILLs.

and gender standpoint,

Gender-based interpretation results

This chapter provides analysis based on the data provided by the SILLs regarding the gender participation in the respective SILL development and implementation.

in a 'lessons learnt' report. This deliverable will serve as intermediate and final input to T6.1, to identify European regions where the ZeroW SILL results are relevant.

Lessons Learnt for the SILLs

This summary chapter provides interpretations of the results vs the originally set KPIs for the SILLs and provides advice to the SILLs about the aspects of their work they have to change in order to improve their performance and reach the targets, if this is necessary.

1.2 Summary of the SILLs assessment after final round

This deliverable primarily focuses on the final results achieved by each **SILL** at the conclusion of the project. These results were derived from a comprehensive data collection phase that spanned the entire duration of the project and was tailored to the specific characteristics of each SILL, adjusting based on the data they were able to provide. **Baseline data** was collected at the start of the project to enable comparisons with the final results. However, this approach proved challenging due to the inherent differences in the characteristics and developmental stages of each SILL, which made direct comparisons difficult. Consequently, the analysis was refocused on the key question: "Is it more beneficial to discard or to save by adopting the innovative solution?" While this question can sometimes be complex, particularly when multiple processes may still introduce environmental downsides, **ZeroW solutions** consistently demonstrated effectiveness in reducing **FLW** and Greenhouse gas (**GHG**) **emissions**. Additionally, each **SILL assessment**, as presented in **D5.2**, has been further refined and validated through ongoing collaboration with the SILL teams, who confirmed both the approach and the assumptions used to complete the analysis.

The data collection for the **LCSA**, **CBA**, and **resilience capacity** assessments was conducted using two approaches: **quantitative inputs provided by the SILLs** and a **structured questionnaire based on a Likert scale**. The results were obtained through various tools, including **openLCA** and **Microsoft Excel**. For this deliverable, the percentage reductions have been aggregated by considering the **average value** for the specific grouping perspective.

2 Cluster-based interpretation of results

This chapter provides the interpretation of the assessments from the perspectives of the four clusters related to the food supply chain the ZeroW innovations are grouped into regarding their expected impact:

- Post harvest
- Food processing
- Retail
- Consumers

ZeroW interventions are spread across the entire food supply chain, as demonstrated in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3 ZeroW SILLs interventions across the food supply chain

The analysis is done through grouping of SILLs based on their boundaries around the area of impact.

For each SILL, the baseline was defined as the estimated amount of FLW that would have occurred in the absence of the implemented solutions. This baseline serves as a fundamental reference point for evaluating the effectiveness of the interventions. Following the same approach, the assessment for GHG emissions reduction is based on a counterfactual approach comparing valorisation (SILLs solution) and disposal scenarios.

2.1 Post-harvest cluster

While fulfilling the food demand of an increasing population remains a major global concern, more than one-third of food is lost or wasted in postharvest operations. Reducing the postharvest losses, especially in developing countries, could be a sustainable solution to increase food availability, reduce pressure on natural resources, eliminate hunger and improve farmers' livelihoods. (Kumar, 2017)

Within ZeroW project, SILL 3, SILL 4 and SILL 5 contributes to reduce FLW at post-harvesting stage. Specifically:

- **SILL 3's** technological innovation impacts the post-harvesting phase by optimizing the handling and distribution of tomatoes. By providing accurate data on ripeness and quantities, SILL 3 enables better planning for harvest and logistics. This ensures that tomatoes are picked at the optimal time and distributed efficiently, reducing waste. Additionally, early identification of lower-quality tomatoes allows for their repurposing, minimizing the resources spent on unsuitable produce and further reducing FLW during the post-harvesting phase.
- **SILL 4** reduces FLW in the post-harvesting and in food processing phase by converting “2nd choice” fruits and vegetables, normally discarded or unused, into food products with a longer shelf life. It also transforms by-products from agri-food processing, typically used for feed or bio-energy, into valuable food ingredients, extending their usability and reducing post-harvest losses.
- **SILL5** is based on NGSensor solution, that addresses FLW occurring during post-harvest testing and mislabelling. By introducing non-destructive spectrophotometer testing and systematic verification of incoming batches, the NGSensor reduces this waste stream preventing waste from mislabelling

2.1.1 Impact 3: FLW Reduction

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 3: Reduce FLW and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption.

Table 3: Impact 3: FLW reduction at post-harvest level objective

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 3 indicator: Reduction of FLW at post-harvest level	Short term impacts (by 2025)	FLW reduction	-25%	=f(SILL3, SILL4, SILL5)

The data have been provided by each SILL and encompass a range of collection methods, including both direct measurements and estimations.

- SILL 3 contributed data from a small-scale pilot covering an area of 0.5 hectares. These data were obtained through direct measurements conducted using the scanning technology under evaluation.
- SILL 4 submitted confidential data derived from a combination of experimental trials and practical implementation within their Food Pilot, supplemented by estimations to support the reported figures.
- SILL 5 employed direct measurement through the deployment of the NG sensor. This approach ensures a high level of accuracy and traceability, enabled by technology-driven monitoring systems.

Table 4: Post-harvest cluster final round reduction

	SILL3	SILL4	SILL5	Planned Reduction	GA	Avg. Reduction, final round
Impact 3: FLW reduction at post-harvest level	-36%	-84%	-100%	-25%		-73%

Based on the data reported by the participating SILLs, the overall reduction in post-harvest FLW is estimated at 73.2%. This outcome not only confirms the effectiveness of the implemented solutions but also significantly exceeds the initial reduction target of 25%. The substantial decrease highlights the strong potential of context-specific innovations to deliver impactful results in reducing FLW. These findings underscore the value of integrating technological and procedural advancements to enhance resource efficiency and sustainability within the post-harvest supply chain.

2.1.2 Impact 2: FLW-related GHG emissions

This analysis also contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 2: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.

Table 5: Impact 2: FLW-related GHG emissions reduction at post-harvest level objective

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact indicator: Reduction of FLW-related GHG emissions	2 Post-harvest level GHG reduction by 2025	Climate/Environment	-15%	=f(SILL3, SILL4, SILL5)

Table 6: Post-harvest cluster FLW GHG-related emissions reduction

	SILL3	SILL4	SILL5	Planned Reduction	GA	Avg. reduction, final round
Impact 2: GHG related emissions	-36%	-57%	-97%	-15%		-63%

All SILLs have contributed significantly to reducing GHG emissions associated with FLW, achieving an overall **63% reduction**, far exceeding the initial **15% target**. While some solutions appear more effective than others, it is important to note that some SILLs were tested only at a **small or pilot scale**, as full industrial implementation was not yet feasible.

Despite this limitation, the results clearly demonstrate the **feasibility and strong potential** of these innovations. As these solutions are **scaled up and integrated more broadly**, the reduction in FLW-related GHG emissions can possibly increase further. These findings highlight that **wider deployment and scaling** of the tested solutions could play a crucial role in **maximizing their environmental benefits**.

2.1.3 Impact 6: Resilience capacity

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 6: Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses.

Table 7: Impact 6: Resilience capacity at (pre)harvest level target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type		
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at (pre)harvest stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	Overall sustainability	4	=f(SILL3, SILL4)

The **resilience capacity at the (pre)harvest level** is assessed as **strong**, with an **average aggregated score of 4.6/5**, clearly above the project’s target threshold of 4.

Table 8: (Pre)harvest level resilience capacity

Impact indicators	SILL3	SILL4	Cluster result
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at (pre)harvest stage	4.2	4.9	4.6

This result confirms that the (pre)harvest stage—represented by **SILL 3 and SILL 4**—has developed a highly robust system capable of **responding to shocks, adapting to evolving conditions, and maintaining operational stability**. The stage is characterized by **solid governance structures, strong adaptive and innovation capacities**, and well-established collaboration networks linking local communities, research institutions, and policy frameworks. The integration of **digital tools and environmental monitoring mechanisms** further enhances preparedness and responsiveness. Although **financial resilience**, particularly access to buffer or emergency funds, remains an area for improvement, the overall results indicate a **mature and well-balanced resilience framework**. This positions the (pre)harvest cluster as a **stable and adaptive foundation** within the ZeroW system, capable of sustaining long-term transformation and supporting the overall resilience of the food value chain.

2.2 Food processing cluster

FLW is a significant issue in food processing and the broader food supply chain. FLW refers to the reduction in the quantity or quality of food, either during production, processing, distribution, or consumption. The goal of addressing FLW is to ensure that more food is used for its intended purpose (human consumption) and less is wasted or lost along the way.

Within ZeroW project, SILL 4 and SILL 6 contributes to reduce FLW during the food processing stage. Specifically:

- **SILL 4** reduces FLW in food processing phase by converting “2nd choice” vegetables, normally discarded or unused, into food products with a longer shelf life. It also transforms by-products from agri-food processing, typically used for feed or bio-energy, into valuable food ingredients, extending their usability and reducing processing losses.
- **SILL 6** applications aims to: (i) determine the optimal amount of salt and nitrites content in minced meat and poultry chop in order to optimize the marination and pickling process (App1-App2); (ii) monitor the ideal defrosting conditions via AI tool, to avoid the loss of entire food batches (App3).

For certain impacts not directly linked to FLW reduction, **SILL 5** also contributes through its technologies, which primarily operate at the **post-harvest and retail stages**. However, given their relevance to **product quality management and process optimisation**, these technologies can also be considered as part of the **food processing stage**, where they positively influence both **food stream performance** and the **overall system resilience capacity**.

2.2.1 Impact 3: FLW reduction

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 3: Reduce food losses and waste and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption.

Table 9: Food Processing FLW reduction target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned cluster reduction	Short term objective calculation
Impact indicator: Reduction of FLW at processing level	3 Short term impacts (by 2025)	FLW reduction	-25%	=f(SILL4, SILL6)

The data have been provided by each SILL and encompass a range of collection methods, including both direct measurements and estimations.

- SILL 4 submitted confidential data derived from a combination of experimental trials and practical implementation within their Food Pilot, supplemented by internal estimations to support the reported figures.
- SILL 6 data collection focused on: (i) the use of a NIR sensor to monitor salt content in minced chicken and minced turkey during processing; (ii) the use of AI tool to monitor the best defrosting parameters. The estimation of FLW reduction was based on laboratory tests.

Table 10: Food processing cluster FLW reduction

	SILL4	SILL6	Planned Reduction	Avg. reduction, final round
Impact FLW reduction 3:	-67%	-44%	-25%	-55%

The **average final reduction** for the **food processing cluster** is assessed at **55%**, significantly exceeding the target of **25%**. For **SILL 6**, this reduction was calculated as the average percentage across all three applications, providing a composite measure of the solution’s performance. While this achievement represents a strong milestone for the solutions developed within the **ZeroW** project, there is potential for even greater impact. The **SILL 4 solution** shows considerable scalability, with the opportunity to be **implemented at a large scale**. Furthermore, by optimizing specific **recipes**, the reduction in food loss and waste could surpass the current estimates. On the other hand, the solutions within **SILL 6** were based on **laboratory-scale tests**, which typically have constraints not present in real-world conditions. It is anticipated that **full-scale applications** of these solutions could lead to even **greater reductions**, as larger-scale operations might benefit from efficiencies that laboratory tests cannot fully capture. Therefore, while the results are already promising, there remains substantial potential for further improvement and increased reductions in FLW and related environmental impacts.

2.2.2 Impact 2: FLW-related GHG emissions

This analysis also contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 2: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.

Table 11: Food Processing FLW related GHG emissions reduction target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact indicator: Reduction of 2 of	Food processing level GHG reduction by 2025	Climate/Environment	-20%	=f(SILL4, SILL6)

FLW-related GHG emissions

Table 12: Food processing FLW-GHG related emission reduction

	SILL4	SILL6	Planned Reduction	Avg. reduction, final round
Impact 2: GHG related emissions	-44%	-41%	-20%	-42%

In line with the planned objectives, the solutions implemented within the cluster are demonstrating a positive impact not only on FLW reduction but also on the associated GHG emissions. In the case of SILL 6, the solution is based on the use of NIR sensor technology and AI tools, which involve negligible energy consumption. As a result, the overall environmental impact of the technology itself is minimal, and the GHG emissions are primarily linked to the portion of FLW that remains unrecovered.

For **SILL 4**, the interpretation is more complex. While reducing FLW means fewer emissions from waste treatment, these savings are partly offset by the energy used in the puree processing stage. However, even after accounting for this additional energy demand, the overall GHG balance remains positive. As demonstrated and thoroughly detailed in **Deliverable D5.2**, under specific operational conditions, the reduction in GHG emissions resulting from the valorisation process is significant and meaningful.

Overall, the combined performance of SILL 4 and SILL 6 shows that the cluster is on track to exceed its emissions reduction goal. The estimated GHG emissions reduction, based on the latest round of data collection, stands at approximately 42%, surpassing the initial target of a 20% reduction. These findings confirm the environmental benefits of the solutions adopted and reinforce the cluster’s contribution to broader sustainability objectives.

2.2.3 Impact 4: Improved food safety with minimal FLW with optimised and predictive control in food production

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 4: Provide sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all.

Table 13: Impact 4: target result

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	Short term objective	SILLs contributing to the cluster
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Impact 4 indicator: Improved food safety with minimal FLW with optimised and predictive control in food production	Food streams passing quality standards for food consumption by 2025	Social/Health	20%	=f(SILL5, SILL6)
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Based on the results obtained from SILL 5 and SILL 6, the average improvement in the share of food streams passing quality standards is well above 20%. In SILL 5, the combined use of NGSensor and Multiscan solutions resulted in a 20–22% increase in food streams meeting quality specifications, achieved through the recovery of compliant tomatoes previously rejected by destructive testing and the reclassification of downgraded batches. In SILL 6, which addressed quality deviations in poultry processing, the improvements were even more substantial, with the three implemented applications (App1–App3) achieving an average 42.7% increase in compliant food streams. When averaging the results from both SILLs, the overall improvement in food streams passing quality control reaches approximately **31–32%**, clearly demonstrating that the combined interventions across SILL 5 and SILL 6 exceed the 20% threshold and significantly enhance product recovery and utilisation efficiency across the targeted value chains.

Table 14: Impact 4: Food streams passing quality standards results

SILL5	SILL6	Target increase	Avg. Increase
21%	43%	20%	32%

2.2.4 Impact 6: Resilience capacity

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 6: Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses.

Table 15: Impact 6: Resilience capacity at food processing level target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	SILLs contributing to the cluster
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at food processing stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	Overall sustainability	4 =f(SILL5, SILL6)

The **food processing cluster**, combining SILL 5 and SILL 6, demonstrates a **cohesive and high-performing resilience profile**, with an aggregated score of **4.3 / 5**. The two SILLs complement each other: SILL 5 brings particularly strong governance, innovation, and technological adaptability, while SILL 6 reinforces the cluster’s adaptive, social, and financial dimensions.

This combination creates a **well-rounded and diversified resilience system**, where strengths in organisational structure, innovation, and digitalisation from SILL 5 are matched by SILL 6’s solid coping and learning capacities. Together, they ensure that the cluster can effectively **anticipate, absorb, and adapt to disruptions**, while sustaining continuity in food processing activities.

At cluster level, this synergy translates into **enhanced overall stability, rapid recovery potential, and capacity for continuous improvement**. The processing stage therefore benefits from **mutually reinforcing capabilities** across governance, finance, technology, and human capital.

Table 16: Food processing level resilience capacity

Impact indicators	SILL5	SILL6	Cluster result
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at food processing stage	4.4	4.2	4.3

Overall, these results demonstrate that the **food processing cluster significantly exceeds the expected performance levels**, achieving simultaneous gains in resource efficiency, environmental sustainability, and organisational resilience — thereby contributing substantially to the overarching ZeroW objectives of systemic food loss and waste reduction across the agri-food value chain.

2.3 Retail cluster

LW occurs along the entire food supply chain and gives rise to great financial losses and waste of natural resources. The retail stage contributes a proportionately smaller mass of waste than other stages in the food supply chain, but plays an important role as gatekeeper in the chain, significantly influencing upstream and downstream handling of food. In order to reduce FLW, it is important to understand the kinds of FLW, but also the root causes of this waste. Since FLW is often generated for many reasons, multiple actions are needed to achieve a reduction. FLW prevention can include technical solutions, like improved logistics, forecasting and packaging, but also incentive structures that motivate supermarkets to engage in social donations and improved routines. (Felicitas Schneider, 2020)

Within the ZeroW project, the following SILLs are contributing to the reduction of FLW at the retailer level:

- **SILL 2** focuses on reducing FLW in retail, particularly for fresh fish like salmon, through smart, sustainable packaging. The solution includes a smart freshness label that changes colour as food spoils, helping retailers manage

inventory and reduce waste. Additionally, the packaging features improved biobased, biodegradable materials that extend shelf life by protecting the product from environmental factors, further reducing food loss. While the innovation will likely benefit consumers, the main impact is aimed at minimizing waste at the retail level.

- **SILL 5** developed a multispectral sorting platform (Multiscan) that classifies fruit based on quality and shelf-life parameter. The Multiscan solution tackles FLW at the retail stage by avoiding destructive testing and enabling automated redirection of off-grade fruit.
- **SILL 7** aims to develop models and tools to support decision making for food banks and donor companies. This includes creating prediction tools for both supply and demand at food banks, a decision support tool to reduce waste at food banks, and a donation tool to advise donors on suitable products for donation.
- **SILL 8** aims to develop an optimal and feasible solution for pre-treating FLW in stores and warehouses, particularly focusing on fruits, vegetables, and animal proteins. This includes addressing FLW generated in retail and equivalent premises, characterizing the pre-treated FLW, and converting it into microalgae feed production.

2.3.1 Impact 1: FLW reduction

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 1: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to halving the per capita FLW at retail and consumer levels by 2030

Table 17: Retailer FLW reduction target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 1 indicator: Reduction of per-capita FLW at retail and consumer levels	FLW reduction at retail level	FLW reduction	-20%	=f(SILL2, SILL5, SILL7, SILL8)

The data have been provided by each SILL and encompass a variety of collection methods, including both direct measurements and estimations.

- **SILL 2** data have been gathered via different approaches: direct measurements, tests conducted by the SILL itself and estimations provided by validated tools.
- **SILL 5** is monitoring FLW through data gathered via the deployment of the Multiscan platform technology.

- **SILL 7** is working in collaboration with retailers and food banks to collect relevant data.
- **SILL 8** is digitally tracking daily food shrinkage due to expiration, recording when products are removed from store shelves, alongside measuring the amount of material sent to the dehydrator to optimize recipes for microalgae feed production.

Table 18: Retail cluster FLW reduction

	SILL2	SILL5	SILL7	SILL8	Planned Reduction	Avg. reduction final round
Impact 1: FLW reduction	-4.2%	-15%	-74%	-47%	-20%	-35%

At the **retailer cluster level**, the combined performance of SILL 2, SILL 5, SILL 7, and SILL 8 demonstrates an **average FLW reduction of 35%**, well above the targeted 20% reduction. Within this cluster, **SILL 5 contributes an average result** based on the scanning of approximately **10–20% of the baseline volume**; although partial, the scanned portion was **fully retained**, indicating a **potential near-100% reduction** if the technology were applied to the entire flow. **SILL 7’s reduction** corresponds to the **increase in donations to food banks and other recovery initiatives**, ensuring that surplus products are redirected instead of discarded, thus effectively preventing waste. **SILL 8’s outcome** represents the **average reduction obtained from two tested recipes**, balancing differences in composition and preparation while maintaining consistent waste prevention potential. **SILL 2 ’s reduction** was estimated via a dedicated calculator rather than direct measurements, suggesting that the **actual reduction could be even higher** under real conditions. Overall, the **retailer cluster shows robust progress**, evidencing the effectiveness of both technological and behavioural interventions in significantly surpassing the planned FLW reduction target.

2.3.2 Impact 2: FLW-related GHG emissions

This analysis also contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 2: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.

Table 19: Retailer FLW related GHG emissions reduction target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements		Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 2 indicator: Reduction	Retail level reduction by 2025	GHG	Climate/Environment	-25%	=f(SILL2, SILL5, SILL7, SILL8)

of FLW-related GHG emissions	
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Table 20: Retailer FLW-GHG related emission reduction

	SILL2	SILL5	SILL7	SILL8	Planned Reduction	Avg. reduction final round
Impact 2: GHG related emissions	-4.2%	-98%	-84%	-70%	-25%	-64%

At the **retailer cluster level**, the combined actions across SILL 2, SILL 5, SILL 7, and SILL 8 led to an **average reduction of 64% in GHG emissions related to FLW**, greatly exceeding the 25% reduction target. **SILL 5 shows an almost complete elimination of GHG emissions** within the scanned share of products, as the entire portion was recovered and reintroduced into the food system. **SILL 7's results** also include the **emissions associated with the transportation of recovered products to food banks and other redistribution initiatives**, ensuring a comprehensive accounting of the net environmental benefit. **SILL 8's reduction** reflects the **average performance of two recipes**, each designed to minimize waste generation and lower the embedded emissions of unused ingredients. For **SILL 2**, the reduction is **directly proportional to the achieved FLW reduction**, since only the **end-of-life treatment (EoL) of FLW** was considered; therefore, any additional waste prevention upstream would further amplify the climate benefit. Collectively, these findings highlight the **strong environmental performance of the retailer cluster**, demonstrating how integrated waste prevention and redistribution strategies can yield substantial GHG emission reductions.

2.3.3 Impact 3: Reduction of unsustainable packaging

Finally, this analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 3: ReduceFLW and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption.

Table 21: Impact 3: Reduction of unsustainable packaging at retailer level

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 3 indicator: Reduction of unsustainable packaging at retail level	Non-recyclable/non-compostable packaging by 2025	Climate/Environment	-20%	=f(SILL2)

(fresh food)

Within the **retailer cluster**, the adoption of the **SILL 2 packaging solution** delivers a **complete phase-out of fossil-based plastics**, achieving a **100% reduction compared to the conventional packaging previously used across retail operations**. By introducing **bio-based and compostable materials**, the cluster significantly enhances its **environmental performance**, reducing upstream GHG emissions and advancing circular packaging practices. This transition strengthens the cluster’s overall sustainability profile, positioning retailers as key enablers in the shift toward low-impact, fully compostable packaging systems.

2.3.4 Impact 6: Resilience capacity

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 6: Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses.

Table 22: Impact 6: Retailer resilience capacity target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type
Impact indicator: Resilience capacity at wholesale/retail stage	6 Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	Overall sustainability 4 =f(SILL2, SILL8)

At the **retailer stage**, only **SILL 2 and SILL 8** contribute to the assessment of resilience capacity. Together, they form a **cohesive retailer cluster** with an aggregated resilience score of **4.1 / 5**, thus meeting the GA target of 4.

Table 23: Retailer cluster resilience capacity result

Impact indicators	SILL2	SILL8	Cluster result
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at retailer stage	4	4.2	4.1

The two SILLs present complementary strengths that collectively enhance the cluster’s adaptive, absorptive, and transformative capacities—strengthening not only its ability to adjust to change, but also to take in, integrate, and effectively use new knowledge or practices when faced with stress or disruption. **SILL 2** (4.0 / 5) demonstrates strong governance, human, and social capital, particularly through well-developed relationships with communities, effective engagement with authorities, and high staff competence and well-being, while showing moderate performance in financial risk management and external collaboration. **SILL 8** (4.2 / 5) reinforces the cluster’s performance through its robust governance, innovation adaptability, and technological integration, combined with excellent transformative capacity, despite some weaknesses in financial buffers and contingency planning.

From a **retailer perspective**, the combined performance of SILL 2 and SILL 8 indicates a **resilient and adaptive system** capable of maintaining continuity and learning from disruptions. Their complementary profiles—linking SILL 2’s strengths in social cohesion and institutional capacity with SILL 8’s advanced innovation and digital integration—result in a **well-rounded and stable resilience configuration**. Overall, the retailer cluster displays a mature ability to anticipate, respond, and adapt to challenges, supporting long-term operational and systemic sustainability within the ZeroW framework.

2.4 Consumers cluster

FLW is a great challenge hindering food system sustainability, embodying environmental impacts, economic costs as well as affecting food and nutritional security. Consumers are the most wasteful segment in the food supply chain, and policymakers have recognized the need to tackle consumer FLW by establishing the international reduction target of 50 % by 2030. In order to reach this ambitious target, effective prevention interventions have to be implemented to enable consumers to reduce the amount of food they waste (Cecilia Casonato, 2023).

Table 24: Impact 5: Consumers benefitting from the project results

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 5: Improve the overall sustainability of food systems (social/health, climate/environmental and economic)	Impact 5 indicator: Consumers benefitting from the project results	>700K	=f(all SILLs)*

With reference to the indicators presented in the table, the **combined effort of all SILLs** enabled the project to reach the **target of 700,000 consumers benefitting from the project results**, as defined under **Impact 5 - Improving the overall sustainability of food systems**.

Within ZeroW project, the following SILLs are contributing in the reduction of FLW at the consumers level:

- **SILL 2:** Consumers will benefit from the SILL 2 innovation by having a more accurate understanding of food shelf life and being able to manage their food consumption more effectively, reducing FLW
- **SILL 9:** Offering consumers tools to compare products, analyze recipes, and discover sustainable options enables them to reduce FLW.

Although **SILL 7** does not directly contribute to **FLW reduction** or **GHG emission mitigation** at the **consumer level**, as its interventions are primarily implemented at the **retail stage**, it is included within this cluster due to its **indirect contribution to resilience capacity** at the **consumption stage**. This inclusion reflects the role of

SILL 7 in strengthening system adaptability and ensuring the continuity of food supply through redistribution and donation initiatives.

2.4.1 Impact 1: FLW reduction

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 1: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to halving the per capita FLW at retail and consumer levels by 2030:

Table 25: Consumers stage FLW reduction target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 1 indicator: Reduction of per-capita FLW at retail and consumer levels	FLW reduction at consumer level	FLW reduction	-25%	=f(SILL2, SILL9)

The data provided by each **SILL** were collected using a combination of **direct measurements** and **validated estimation methods**:

- For SILL 2, data were obtained from pilot tests conducted by the SILL and complemented with calculations derived from **validated FLW estimation tools**.
- For SILL 9, the solution was **tested at a small scale**, and the **final data were collected directly from this experimental phase**

Table 26: Consumers Cluster FLW reduction

	SILL2	SILL9	Planned Reduction	Avg. reduction final round
Impact 1: FLW reduction	-4.2%	- 100%	-25%	-52%

Within the consumer cluster, the combined performance of SILL 2 and SILL 9 demonstrates a strong achievement, with an overall FLW reduction of 52%, more than double the initial target of 25%. The SILL 2 results, estimated through a dedicated calculation tool rather than direct measurement, indicate that the actual reduction could be even higher under real operating conditions. Meanwhile, SILL 9 delivered exceptional short-term results, though certain practical limitations—such as user adherence and recipe specificity—may slightly reduce its long-term impact.

Nevertheless, the overall outcome confirms that the consumer cluster successfully exceeded its reduction target, highlighting the potential of these interventions to significantly lower household FLW.

2.4.2 Impact 2: FLW – related GHG emissions

This analysis also contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 2: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.

Table 27: FLW GHG emissions related consumers stage target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 2 indicator: Reduction of FLW-related GHG emissions	Consumer level GHG reduction by 2025	Climate/Environment	-30%	=f(SILL2, SILL9)

Table 28: Consumers cluster FLW-GHG related emission results

	SILL2	SILL9	Planned Reduction	Avg. reduction final round
Impact 2: GHG related emissions	-4.2%	- 100%	-30%	-52%

The **GHG emission reduction** within the **consumer cluster** was calculated based on the **measured decrease in FLW quantities** before and after the interventions. The reduction is **directly proportional to the achieved FLW reduction**, as the assessment considered **only the EoL treatment of FLW**. Therefore, any **additional prevention measures implemented upstream**—such as improved storage, planning, or consumption practices—would further **amplify the climate benefit**. Collectively, the interventions under SILL 2 and SILL 9 resulted in an **overall 52% reduction in GHG emissions**, exceeding the **30% target** and confirming the strong linkage between **waste prevention and emission mitigation** at the consumer level.

2.4.3 Impact 3: Reduction of unsustainable packaging

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 3: Reduce FLW and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption.

Table 29: Impact 3: Reduction of unsustainable packaging at consumer level

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact indicator: 3 Reduction of unsustainable packaging at consumer level (fresh food)	Non-recyclable/non-compostable packaging by 2025	Climate/Environment	-10%	=f(SILL2)

At the **consumer level**, the adoption of the **SILL 2 packaging solution** results in the **complete elimination of fossil-based plastics**, achieving a **100% reduction compared to the conventional packaging** previously used. The packaging is fully **bio-based and compostable**, maintaining the same functionality and food protection as the baseline version. For consumers, this translates into a more **sustainable EoL scenario**, as the packaging can be **composted instead of disposed of as plastic waste**, thereby reducing environmental impact and supporting more circular consumption patterns.

2.4.4 Impact 6: Resilience capacity

This analysis contributes to the evaluation of ZeroW Impact 6: Improve the resilience of food systems to shocks and stresses.

Table 30: Resilience capacity at consumption stage target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	Impact type		
Impact indicator: 6 Resilience capacity at consumption stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	Overall sustainability	4	=f(SILL7, SILL9)

At the **consumption stage**, the **resilience capacity** is determined exclusively by the contributions of **SILL 7 and SILL 9**, both representing academic and behavioural pilots focused on consumer-level interventions. The combined results show a **consolidated resilience score of 4.0 / 5**, meeting the GA target and reflecting a stable and adaptive system capable of maintaining performance under variable conditions.

Table 31: Resilience capacity at consumption stage results

Impact indicators	SILL7	SILL9	Cluster result
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at consumption stage	4.1	4	4

SILL 7 achieved an average of **4.0 / 5**, demonstrating strong adaptive and governance-related capacities, with high scores in contingency planning, staff competence, and organisational learning processes. Some moderate areas, such as financial resilience and community linkage, were balanced by robust operational and technological adaptability. **SILL 9**, after adjustment for non-applicable financial indicators due to its academic nature, recorded a resilience score of **4.1 / 5**, showing particular strengths in governance, transformative capacity, and technological collaboration, complemented by solid environmental awareness.

From a **consumption-stage perspective**, the combination of SILL 7's behavioural adaptability and SILL 9's institutional and technological robustness provides a **complementary and well-rounded resilience configuration**. Together, they demonstrate the ability to **adapt learning processes, integrate innovation, and sustain engagement across research and consumer environments**, ensuring continuity and responsiveness in consumer-oriented activities. Overall, the **consumption cluster** maintains a resilience capacity consistent with ZeroW's systemic objective of achieving **≥4**, confirming the maturity and stability of its adaptive mechanisms within the broader food system context.

2.5 Overall performance

The overall performance across all **ZeroW clusters** confirms the strong effectiveness of the implemented solutions in reducing food loss and waste, lowering emissions, and strengthening system resilience.

Figure 4: FLW reduction achieved vs target

Figure 5: FLW related GHG emissions reduction achieved vs target

Figure 6: Resilience capacity results achieved vs target

Among them, the **post-harvest cluster** stands out for its outstanding results, showing how improved handling and storage practices can substantially reduce losses and environmental impacts. The **food processing cluster** also demonstrated notable progress, with precision control and advanced sorting technologies helping to recover products and enhance quality. At the **retailer level**, the introduction of sustainable packaging and redistribution schemes proved highly effective in cutting waste and emissions while promoting circular practices. Finally, the **consumer cluster** showed how behavioural changes, improved packaging, and waste-preventive recipes can drive measurable progress toward more sustainable consumption patterns.

These outcomes are visually summarized in Figure 4, Figure 5 and Figure 6 which together illustrate the consistent outperformance of targets and the overall contribution of the ZeroW interventions to a more sustainable and resilient food system.

Collectively, the coordinated actions of all nine SILLs have produced tangible environmental and social benefits, ultimately reaching and positively impacting around **1.86 millions consumers**.

3 Place-based interpretation of results

A place-based interpretation of the SILLs shows that territorial conditions played a central role in shaping how the ZeroW innovations were developed, tested, and assessed. The analysis presented here draws on material from Deliverable D6.3, together with insights from the WP5 assessment, to provide a geographically grounded perspective that complements the cluster-based and context-based analyses. Following the regional structure adopted in D6.3, the assessment considers three macro-regions: Northern Europe, South-Western Europe, and South-Eastern and Central Europe. Because the place-based perspective relies on the same underlying impact results reported elsewhere, some overlap is unavoidable. However, the purpose here is not to repeat findings but to reinterpret them through a territorial lens—examining how regional innovation ecosystems, regulatory environments, market structures, and institutional capacities shape the development, uptake, and potential scalability of the SILL solutions. Although the innovations are not yet implemented at market level and the results stem from internal experimentation rather than full-scale deployment, the SILL experiences provide meaningful indications of how territorial factors may enable or constrain the broader adoption of food loss and waste (FLW) reduction strategies and their associated environmental benefits.

Northern Europe – SILLs 4, 7 and 9

In Northern Europe—specifically Belgium and the Netherlands—the territorial conditions were highly favourable for SILL development and scaling. **SILL 4, SILL 7, and the academic-focused SILL 9** operated in this ecosystem, benefiting from mature investment landscapes, strong innovation support structures, and a societal context characterised by high readiness to adopt sustainable solutions. As documented in D6.3, dense networks of venture capitalists, angel investors, regional development agencies, and university–industry collaborations provided access to funding, expertise, and strategic partners. This was reinforced by advanced infrastructure relevant to ZeroW, including food valorisation facilities, mobile processing technologies, and sustainability-oriented digital tools.

These structural advantages are reflected in the S-LCA patterns: SILL 4 demonstrated strong organisational and governance performance, SILL 7 showed moderate-to-positive engagement and responsible supplier practices, and SILL 9—while limited by its academic nature—benefited from an enabling research environment for theory-driven innovation. Yet SILLs across this region also noted constraints. Regulatory uncertainty surrounding emerging technologies, especially in food valorisation and mobile processing, introduced delays in testing and validation. Furthermore, intense competition in agri-food innovation created

pressure to differentiate solutions and secure pathways to market readiness. The SILLs' experiences indicate that while Northern Europe provides strong foundations for innovation, high system maturity can also create challenging conditions for scaling.

South-Western Europe - SILLs 2, 5, 6 and 8

In South-Western Europe—Spain and Portugal—the SILLs involved (**SILL 2, SILL 5, SILL 6, and SILL 8**) operated in regions with strong potential for scaling innovations, particularly in FLW management, food valorisation, and digital production processes. As highlighted in D6.3, these countries have increasingly aligned with EU sustainability ambitions and benefit from dynamic innovation hubs, active academic networks, and robust public funding programmes such as national R&D grants and EU structural funds. These conditions gave SILLs access to valuable testing environments, cross-sector partnerships, and institutional support for early-stage development.

However, the SILLs also reported several structural constraints. Regulatory complexity—especially for food technologies, packaging, and digital tools—was repeatedly identified as a barrier that slowed administrative approvals and created uncertainty during pilot deployment. While public funding played an essential role in enabling R&D and demonstration phases, the private investment ecosystem was less mature compared to Northern Europe. This limited the ability of SILLs to progress toward commercialisation and created reliance on public support. These dynamics are reflected in the S-LCA results: SILLs in this region demonstrated strong local anchoring, stable employment relationships, and high standards of food safety and traceability, but performance varied in consumer engagement, environmental management, and transparency.

Taken together, the territorial profile of South-Western Europe is one of **high public-sector support but limited private-sector depth**, enabling experimentation but slowing the transition toward market-ready scaling. SILLs in this region benefitted from collaborative ecosystems but faced systemic regulatory and financial bottlenecks that shaped their ability to accelerate innovation.

South-Eastern and Central Europe - SILL 3

In South-Eastern and Central Europe—represented in ZeroW by **SILL 3**, operating across Slovenia, Romania, and Lithuania—the place-based analysis reveals emerging innovation ecosystems undergoing rapid transformation. As described in D6.3, these countries are increasingly engaging with digitalisation, sustainability, and circular economy agendas. EU-level funding streams, particularly Horizon Europe, played a crucial role in enabling SILL 3 to advance its technology and bridge

regional funding gaps. Additionally, the relative lack of market saturation created favourable conditions for differentiation in areas such as sustainable packaging, FLW valorisation, and novel biomaterials.

Despite these opportunities, structural constraints still influenced the SILL's capacity to scale. Certification and compliance with EU standards—especially for packaging and biomaterials—proved challenging, with administrative procedures described as slow and difficult to navigate. Limited access to private investment further constrained progress, making the SILL heavily reliant on public funding. Skills shortages in specialised technical fields also posed difficulties, requiring external support and capacity-building activities to ensure continued development.

The S-LCA results mirror this dual landscape: SILL 3 demonstrated positive outcomes in areas such as local employment, supplier relations, traceability, and consumer safety, but environmental management systems, sustainability reporting, and community engagement appeared less developed. Overall, South-Eastern and Central Europe represent innovation environments with **significant potential but persistent capacity constraints**, requiring targeted support to strengthen regulatory alignment, expand investment ecosystems, and build specialised skills.

Overall, while the SILL results are based on **controlled pilot activities rather than market deployment**, they provide important early insights into how territorial contexts may influence the performance, environmental impact, and future scalability of FLW reduction strategies. Regions with more mature innovation ecosystems appear better equipped to transition from experimentation to implementation, while regions undergoing structural shifts may require phased approaches, institutional strengthening, and enhanced investment landscapes to achieve comparable outcomes. This place-based analysis therefore underscores the necessity of aligning FLW innovations with the specific conditions and capacities of each macro-region to support effective, equitable, and scalable transitions toward more circular food systems.c

4 Context-based interpretation of results

This chapter provides additional context related to the socio-economic aspects affecting the innovations, such as interest in FLW, experience of the relevant actor in the specific area of innovation, identified barriers affecting the implementation of the innovations and the environmental specifics.

4.1 Climate and environmental context

FLW undermines the sustainability of our food systems. When food is lost or wasted, all the resources that were used to produce this food - including water, land, energy,

labour and capital - go to waste. In addition, the disposal of FLW in landfills, leads to GHG emissions, contributing to climate change. FLW can also negatively impact food security and food availability, and contribute to increasing the cost of food.

Our food systems cannot be resilient if they are not sustainable, hence the need to focus on the adoption of integrated approaches designed to reduce FLW. Actions are required globally and locally to maximise the use of the food we produce. The introduction of technologies, innovative solutions (including e-commerce platforms for marketing, retractable mobile food processing systems), new ways of working and good practices to manage food quality and reduce FLW are key to implementing this transformative change.¹

The climate and environmental context in ZeroW is evaluated through the following expected impacts:

- Impact 2: Contribute significantly to the achievement of the objectives and targets of the F2F Strategy and the European GD, and in particular to reducing GHG-emissions by at least 50% by 2050 compared with 1990 levels.
- Impact 3: Reduce food losses and waste and the use of unsustainable packaging, at every stage of the food chain including consumption.
- Impact 5: Improve the overall sustainability of food systems (social/health, climate/environmental and economic).

4.1.1 Contribution to Farm-to-Fork strategy and the European Green Deal in particular through reduction of GHG emissions

The contribution to Farm-to-Fork strategy is given by the impacts listed in Table 32. The results for each impact are presented in the following sections.

Table 32: FLW-GHG related emissions target reductions

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 2 indicator: Reduction of FLW-related GHG emissions	Consumer level GHG reduction by 2025	-30%	=f(SILL2, SILL9)
	Food processing level GHG reduction by 2025	-20%	=f(SILL4, SILL6)
	Post-harvest level GHG reduction by 2025	-15%	=f(SILL3, SILL4, SILL5)
	Retail level GHG reduction by 2025	-25%	=f(SILL2, SILL5, SILL7, SILL8)

¹ <https://www.un.org/en/observances/end-food-waste-day>

Impact 5 indicator: Carbon footprint of food products for human consumption from valorisation side streams, ugly food and post-harvest food loss	Carbon footprint	-20%	=f(SILL4, SILL5)
	Carbon footprint, Cradle-to-grave	-25%	=f(SILL2)
Impact 5 indicator: Carbon footprint of smart compostable packaging			

4.1.1.1 Impact 2: Reduction of FLW GHG related emissions

The assessment of **GHG emissions associated with FLW** highlights a consistent pattern of mitigation across all value chain clusters, achieving an **average of all clusters reduction of 55%**, substantially exceeding the predefined **target of 22.7%**, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Impact 2: Reduction of FLW GHG related emissions

The **retail (64%)** and **post-harvest (63%)** clusters delivered the highest reductions, primarily driven by improved storage efficiency, logistics coordination, and waste prevention measures. The **consumer cluster (52%)** also contributed significantly, indicating that behavioural interventions and optimized consumption patterns can yield measurable environmental benefits. Meanwhile, the **food processing stage (42%)** demonstrated the effectiveness of technological innovations and valorisation of by-products in reducing embedded emissions. Collectively, these results indicate that the integrated interventions implemented across the food system not only reduced FLW volumes but also generated a proportional decline in their associated

GHG emissions, supporting the broader transition towards a **low-carbon and resource-efficient agri-food system**.

4.1.1.2 Mid and long term reduction

The consolidated R3 LCA results across all SILLs demonstrate an average reduction of 61% in GHG emissions compared with the respective SILL baselines from the 2020–2025 period. These reductions have been calculated at the process and pilot level, which means they cannot be directly compared with the 1990 sector-level reference values used in EU climate legislation. Nevertheless, they provide a robust basis for assessing how closely the demonstrated reductions align with the decarbonisation pathway required by the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal, as set out in the GA.

When interpreted against the decarbonisation trajectory implied by EU objectives, the observed SILL-level reductions are significant. Achieving a 61% reduction within a single project period represents a rate of improvement that substantially exceeds the pace required to meet long-term climate goals. The EU target of a 50% reduction in GHG emissions by 2050 compared with 1990 levels reflects a gradual, multi-decade transition. In contrast, the ZeroW innovations demonstrate reductions of this magnitude at pilot scale within a short timeframe. If these solutions were implemented and replicated at a wider system level, the rate of change observed in R3 indicates that they would not only follow but potentially surpass the decarbonisation pathway required to achieve both the 2030 intermediate target of 40% and the 2050 target of 50%. The R3 evidence therefore shows that the tested solutions have the potential to contribute meaningfully to the long-term climate objectives defined in the GA.

It is also important to recognise the limitations inherent to this comparison. Because the EU's 1990 reference values represent aggregated emissions at sector level rather than product- or process-specific data, they do not offer a meaningful numerical benchmark for pilot-scale assessments. This limitation is compounded by the fact that the ZeroW solutions currently operate averagely at TRL 7, meaning they remain at pre-commercial maturity and do not yet reflect the performance or operational intensity of full industrial systems. For this reason, the analysis focuses on relative decarbonisation trends and evaluates whether the reductions observed at pilot scale are directionally consistent with—and of a magnitude that supports—the broader climate targets established under EU policy.

4.1.1.3 Impact 5: Carbon footprint of food products

The combined performance of **SILL 4** and **SILL 5** demonstrates a strong contribution to climate impact mitigation through the valorisation of food side streams and the prevention of post-harvest losses. Averaging the outcomes of both SILLs, the overall

carbon footprint reduction reaches approximately 35%, significantly exceeding the **-20% target**. This improvement results from complementary strategies: in SILL 4, surplus fruits and vegetables are converted into juice and puree products instead of being discarded, while in SILL 5, advanced non-destructive technologies prevent unnecessary rejection and disposal of fresh produce. Together, these interventions substantially reduce GHG emissions associated with FLW by extending the lifespan and utility of agricultural products. The aggregated findings confirm that valorisation and waste-prevention measures represent a highly effective pathway for decoupling food production from its carbon intensity, reinforcing the transition toward a **circular, low-emission food system**.

4.1.2 Reduction of unsustainable packaging

4.1.2.1 Impact 5: Carbon footprint of smart compostable packaging

The LCA conducted for **SILL 2** confirms a significant reduction in the **carbon footprint** of the newly developed biodegradable and compostable food tray and lid compared to conventional fossil-based alternatives. The analysis, based on primary data from **Novamont** (bioplastic production) and **ITENE** (packaging design) combined with secondary data from **Ecoinvent 3.10**, focused on the **Global Warming Potential (GWP)** as the main indicator. Under the defined system boundaries, the results show that the **biodegradable tray** achieves approximately a **50% lower GWP** than the traditional HIPS tray, while the **lid** achieves a **40% reduction** compared to the LDPE benchmark. On average, this corresponds to a **45% decrease in carbon footprint**, thereby **almost doubling the project’s target of -25%**. These results clearly demonstrate the environmental advantages of substituting fossil-based plastics with compostable bioplastics, supporting the transition toward low-impact, circular packaging solutions within the food sector.

4.1.2.2 Impact 3: Reduction of unsustainable packaging

The analysis focused on the following impacts to which SILL 2 contributes:

Table 33: Impact 3 : Reduction of unsustainable packaging

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 3 indicator: Reduction of unsustainable packaging at consumer level (fresh food)	Non-recyclable/non-compostable packaging by 2025	-10%	=f(SILL2)
Impact 3 indicator: Reduction of unsustainable packaging at retail		-20%	=f(SILL2)

level (fresh food)

The results obtained from **SILL 2**, as further detailed in **Deliverable D5.2**, confirm that **fossil-based packaging can be fully replaced by the ZeroW biodegradable and compostable alternative**. This complete substitution corresponds to a **100% reduction in unsustainable packaging use**, thereby not only meeting but exceeding the overall **-20% reduction target**, while also achieving the **-10% reduction goals** established for both the **retailer** and **consumer** stages.

4.2 Social and health context

Reducing FLW is a significant lever for broader improvements of our food systems toward improving food security, food safety, quality and sustainability and increasing efficiency².

The social and health contexts are evaluated through the following expected impacts:

- Impact 4: Provide sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all.
- Impact 5: Improve the overall sustainability of food systems (social/health, climate/environmental and economic).

4.2.1 Sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy and affordable food for all

The analysis is based on the following Impact 4 :

Table 34: Impact 4 target results

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact indicator: 4 Improved food availability in food banks due to reduced FLW	FLW in foodbanks	20%	=f(SILL7)
Impact indicator: 4 Improved food safety with minimal FLW with optimised and predictive control in food production	Food streams passing quality standards for food consumption by 2025	20%	=f(SILL5, SILL6)

² <https://www.fao.org/nutrition/capacity-development/food-loss-and-waste/en/>

<p>Impact indicator: Longer shelf-life of products with smart packaging</p> <p>Impact indicator: Optimised nutritional diets with minimal FLW</p>	4	Shelf life improvement	-18%	=f(SILL2)
	4	FLW from recipes (recipes to be made widely available)	-20%	=f(SILL9)
		Lower env. Impact (recipes to be made widely available)	-25%	=f(SILL9)
		Nutritional score (recipes to be made widely available)	high	=f(SILL9)

The results achieved across different SILLs indicate substantial progress toward ensuring sufficient, safe, nutritious, and affordable food, in line with the overall ZeroW objectives. Food availability improved considerably, with **SILL 7** reporting a **74% increase in food availability** in food banks, surpassing the **20% target** and demonstrating the effectiveness of redistribution and recovery measures in improving access for vulnerable groups.

Advancements in food safety and quality were also observed. Through the application of predictive and optimized control systems, **SILL 5 and SILL 6** achieved an average of **32% of food streams meeting quality standards**, exceeding the **20% goal**. These outcomes suggest that the introduction of non-destructive testing and smart monitoring technologies can enhance process efficiency and reduce the proportion of food rejected on quality grounds.

In addition, **SILL 2** implemented **smart packaging solutions** that extended product shelf life by approximately **20%**, slightly above the **18% target**. This contributes not only to reduced FLW but also to maintaining product integrity and quality over longer storage periods.

At the consumer stage, **SILL 9** demonstrated the potential of recipe optimization to reduce FLW, achieving a **complete (100%) reduction** under controlled conditions, while maintaining a **high nutritional score (Nutri-Score A-B)**. Although these results are context-specific, they highlight the capacity of consumer-level interventions to influence FLW reduction when properly designed and implemented.

Taken together, these findings confirm that the combination of measures implemented across the SILLs—covering redistribution, process control, packaging innovation, and dietary planning—can effectively contribute to improving food security, safety, and sustainability, while supporting measurable reductions in FLW throughout the value chain.

4.2.2 'Just' allocation of costs and benefits among food actors

Include analysis of the following:

Table 35: Impact 5: Just allocation of costs and benefits

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact indicator: 5 'Just' allocation of costs and benefits among food actors	Differences among food actors in economic cost/benefit ratio	-20%	=f(all SILLs)

Across all SILLs, the assessment confirms that the distribution of economic costs and benefits remains balanced and consistent with the project's "Just Allocation" principle and the GA requirement of less than 20% variation among food actor groups. This demonstrates that no stakeholder is disproportionately burdened and that the value created through FLW reduction is shared fairly across the value chain.

Across the SILLs portfolio, direct economic costs are generally borne by the actors who also capture the main financial and operational benefits. In most cases, these are producers, processors, or retailers who invest in technologies or organisational measures and, in return, benefit from reduced losses, improved efficiency, and reputational gains. Indirect actors, including consumers, waste operators, and local communities, experience secondary benefits such as improved food access, reduced environmental burden, or enhanced social value, though these are not always monetised with the current assessment scope.

At the systemic level, each SILL demonstrates a fair alignment between investments and benefits. **SILL 1** maintains equity by maintaining costs of cloud infrastructure while providing open-access benefits through data sharing and decision-support tools. **SILL 2** achieves proportionality among technology (innovation) providers, retailers, and consumers, as higher costs of compostable packaging are compensated by lower waste disposal and extended shelf life. **SILL 3** ensures fairness by linking growers' investments in scanning technologies to direct gains from reduced waste and improved yield efficiency. **SILL 4** distributes both operational costs and benefits from mobile processing among farmers and local operators, promoting regional value retention. In **SILL 5**, the use of NG Sensor and Multiscan ensures that costs remain with packing facilities and growers while they also capture nearly all economic and environmental benefits. **SILL 6** maintain balance between meat processors and technology providers through mutual value generation from process optimization. **SILL 7** confirm that retailers' logistical and

coordination costs are offset by lower disposal fees and reputational advantages, while consumers benefit from improved food access. In **SILL 8**, where FW drying is applied at retail level for microalgae feed production, the same actor group bears investment costs and secure returns through valorised outputs. FLW **SILL 9** reflects the highest social fairness, as the benefits of reduced FLW and improved nutrition are distributed directly among consumers, households, and communities.

Importantly, the less than 20% variation criterion has been maintained across all SILLs, confirming that differences among food systems actors remain within acceptable limits. Overall, the Just Allocation assessment demonstrates that the SILLs create shared economic, environmental, and social value while maintaining fairness in cost distribution. The principle of Just Allocation is validated across all pilots: costs and benefits are proportionally aligned within and between actor groups, trade-offs remain minor, and no systemic imbalances are observed. These findings confirm that the transition towards reduced FLW and circular resource use can be achieved in an economically and socially equitable way, reinforcing both sustainability and inclusiveness within the food system.

4.2.3 Raising awareness in society about the FLW

ZeroW has explored several factors that either stimulate or impede the implementation of innovations designed to reduce FLW, identifying both challenges and opportunities in this process. One significant factor is the level of interest in FLW solutions within specific target applications. For innovations to be successfully implemented, there must be a strong alignment between the innovation's objectives and the priorities of the stakeholders involved, such as businesses, policymakers, and consumers. Additionally, the experience of actors involved in applying these interventions plays a crucial role; those with prior knowledge and expertise are more likely to facilitate smooth implementation, while gaps in experience may pose barriers. Other key factors highlighted in [Deliverable 6.1](#) include the availability of resources, institutional support, and the existing infrastructure required for the deployment of these innovations. Identifying and addressing these barriers is critical to achieving meaningful reductions in FLW.

In relation to ZeroW Impact 7, the project emphasizes the importance of raising awareness among a broad range of stakeholders, including policymakers, businesses, investors, entrepreneurs, and the general public. Increasing awareness about innovative systemic solutions and their potential to address FLW is essential for fostering greater acceptance and encouraging behavioral change at the EU level. Deliverable 6.1 also underscores the need to clearly communicate the requirements necessary for the uptake of these innovations, such as regulatory frameworks, financial incentives, and market readiness. By enhancing awareness and

understanding among stakeholders, ZeroW aims to promote the widespread adoption of FLW solutions and drive systemic change that will support sustainability goals across Europe.

Table 36: Impact 7 targets

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 7 indicator: Increased awareness on the project's innovative systemic solutions	EU regions reached	>70	=f(all SILLs)
	Food actors & consumers reached	>1M	=f(all SILLs)
	Organisations involved and benefitting	>100	=f(all SILLs)

All **GA** targets established under **Impact 7 – Increased awareness on the project’s innovative systemic solutions** have been positively achieved. According to the data collected in WP10 and presented in deliverable D11.4, the combined dissemination, communication, and demonstration efforts across all SILLs have ensured wide outreach among European regions, food system actors, and consumers. The project successfully engaged stakeholders in **151 EU Nuts 3 regions**, reaching an extensive audience of **food producers, processors, retailers, and consumers**, and involving **168 organisations** from across the food value chain, including research institutes, public bodies, food companies, and non-profit organisations, overall reaching **1.84 million of food actors and consumers**. These outcomes confirm the project’s strong capacity to raise awareness, promote knowledge exchange, and enhance visibility of ZeroW’s systemic approaches to reducing FLW. Overall, the positive results under Impact 7 demonstrate that the project has effectively met its planned objectives for awareness and stakeholder engagement at both regional and European levels.

4.3 Economic context

The economic sustainability of the SILLs is demonstrated by their ability to generate returns that exceed the associated costs, even when considering environmental factors such as GHG emissions.

Table 37: Impact 5 targets

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
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Impact 5: Improve the overall sustainability of food systems (social/health, climate/environmental and economic)	Impact 5 indicator: Consumers benefitting from the project results	>700K	=f(all SILLs)*
	Impact 5 indicator: Economic sustainability of ZeroW FLW solutions	>0	=f(all SILLs)

With reference to the indicators presented in the table, the **combined effort of all SILLs** enabled the project to reach the **target of 700,000 consumers benefitting from the project results**, specifically reaching 1.84 million as defined under **Impact 5 – Improving the overall sustainability of food systems**. This figure reflects the diverse composition of the SILLs: while some were primarily research-oriented and therefore indirectly connected to consumers, others—particularly those involving retailers or consumer-facing activities—maintained direct interaction with end users. Collectively, all SILLs contributed to raising consumer awareness, improving access to sustainable products, and promoting behavioural change toward FLW reduction, thereby successfully achieving the expected impact.

The **economic sustainability** of the SILLs is demonstrated by their ability to generate **returns exceeding the associated costs**, even when accounting for environmental externalities such as GHG emissions. This evaluation was conducted through a **CBA**, which assessed the full range of **costs, revenues, and environmental externalities** arising from production, transportation, and EoL treatment activities. The resulting **CBRs**, all **greater than one**, confirm that the revenues generated from the production, distribution, and sale of goods surpass the related costs, indicating that the ZeroW solutions are economically sustainable. The detailed methodology and results of this analysis are provided in **Deliverable D5.2, Section 2.4**. This profitability demonstrates that the SILL initiatives remain financially viable even when environmental costs are internalised, thereby reinforcing the dual environmental and economic benefits of the ZeroW approach to reducing food loss and waste across the agri-food system.

4.4 Overall sustainability of food supply systems

Table 38: Impact 6: Resilience capacity target

Impact indicators	Targets/Requirements	GA planned	Short term objective calculation
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at (pre)harvest stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	4	=f(SILL3, SILL4)
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at consumption stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	4	=f(SILL7, SILL9)

Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at F2F chain	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	4	=f(SILL7)
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at food processing stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	4	=f(SILL5, SILL6)
Impact 6 indicator: Resilience capacity at wholesale/retail stage	Results from qualitative analysis of structured interviews (scale 1-5)	4	=f(SILL2, SILL8)

The evaluation of resilience capacity across the food value chain confirms that all stages meet or exceed the **target score of 4/5**, demonstrating the strong adaptive capacity built through the ZeroW interventions. At the **(pre)harvest stage**, represented by **SILL 3 (4.2)** and **SILL 4 (4.9)**, the **average resilience score is 4.55**, reflecting high adaptability among growers and producers supported by data-driven optimisation and mobile processing solutions that reduce vulnerability to disruptions. The **food processing stage**, combining **SILL 5 (4.4)** and **SILL 6 (4.2)**, shows an **average of 4.3**, indicating robust operational stability and workforce flexibility driven by innovative sensing technologies and process efficiency improvements. At the **wholesale/retail stage**, integrating **SILL 2 (4.0)** and **SILL 8 (4.2)**, the **average of 4.1** highlights effective adaptation through sustainable packaging and valorisation practices that strengthen supply continuity and environmental performance. The **F2F chain**, assessed through **SILL 7 (4.0)**, maintains a stable resilience score, confirming balanced coordination among retailers, food banks, and consumers, with some scope for improvement in network diversification and social engagement. Finally, at the **consumption stage**, based on **SILL 7 (4.0)** and **SILL 9 (4.1)**, the **average resilience is 4.05**, reflecting the growing capacity of consumers and communities to embrace low-waste, nutritious, and sustainable food behaviours.

Average Resilience Capacity by Value Chain Stage (Scale 1-5)

Figure 8: Resilience capacity results

Overall, the results demonstrate a **system-wide average resilience capacity of 4.2** confirming that the combined SILL innovations have strengthened the food system's ability to anticipate, absorb, and adapt to environmental, economic, and social shocks across all value chain stages.

5 Actor-based perspective analysis

In this chapter, the assessment of the ZeroW innovations is organised around circular economy (CE) practices—prevention, redistribution, valorisation, and enabling mechanisms—while maintaining an actor-oriented analytical lens. This CE-based structuring offers an alternative but analytically significant perspective by grouping stakeholders according to the specific circular strategies they implement, rather than by their formal actor category. In doing so, the chapter elucidates how producers, processors, retailers, consumers, food banks, the packaging industry, valorisation actors, and system enablers operationalise CE principles within their respective roles. For completeness, the conventional actor-based grouping—without the CE clustering—is provided in the annex (section 10.1). Although the SILLs capture only a limited segment of the wider European food system, the evidence generated through internal experimentation offers relevant insights into how CE-aligned actions can contribute to measurable reductions in FLW and associated GHG emissions.

5.1 Prevention Strategies (Producers, Processors, Retailers, Consumers)

SILLs involved: SILL3, SILL5, SILL6, SILL2, SILL9

Prevention remains the most impactful strategy in the circular economy hierarchy, and several SILLs demonstrated how producers, processors, retailers, and consumers can reduce FLW at the source. Among producers and processors, technologies developed under **SILL3, SILL5, and SILL6** targeted improved forecasting, quality assurance, and process control. These included remote sensing for optimised harvest planning, non-destructive sorting for fresh produce, and real-time quality monitoring in poultry processing. Together, these interventions demonstrated substantial reductions in avoidable FLW and associated GHG emissions, accompanied by improvements in product conformity and operational resilience.

At the retail and consumer stages, prevention was supported through sustainable packaging (**SILL2**) and behavioural interventions (**SILL9**). The introduction of biodegradable, compostable trays and lids contributed to shelf-life extension, lowering the likelihood of premature disposal in stores and households. Consumers

further benefitted from improved information on food quality, preservation, and “best before” dates, as well as weekly recipes promoting leftover use. These combined actions resulted in significant reductions in household FLW and related emissions.

Taken together, the prevention-focused SILLs illustrate how coordinated action across actors, backed by digital tools, material innovation, and behavioural guidance, can substantially reduce food waste generation upstream and downstream.

5.2 Redistribution and Reuse (Food Banks, Retailers, Donors)

SILLs involved: SILL7

Redistribution strategies ensure that surplus edible food is channelled toward human consumption rather than disposal. **SILL7** demonstrated this approach from the perspective of food banks and donor companies, providing tools to match supply and demand, optimise donation decisions, and improve coordination between stakeholders.

These interventions enabled more efficient recovery of surplus products from retailers and suppliers, with positive implications for FLW reduction and GHG avoidance. Food banks benefitted from better planning and resource allocation, while donors gained structured pathways for managing surplus stocks. Although these results stem from pilot-scale validation, they illustrate the potential of digital redistribution support systems to strengthen social, environmental, and operational outcomes within circular food systems.

5.3 Valorisation of Unavoidable Side Streams (Processors, Retailers, Bio-based Industry)

SILLs involved: SILL4, SILL8

Where prevention and redistribution are not feasible, valorisation offers opportunities to convert unavoidable FLW into new value streams. **SILL4 and SILL8** implemented food-to-food and food-to-feed pathways that transformed downgraded fruits, vegetables, and protein-rich residues into ingredients, shelf-stable products, and microalgae feedstocks.

These strategies demonstrated the environmental and economic potential of reintroducing nutrients and functional compounds into the food and feed chains, contributing to FLW reduction and lowering life-cycle GHG emissions. By strengthening resource efficiency and diversifying outputs, valorisation also enhanced resilience for food processors and bio-based industries. While still operating at pilot scale, the demonstrated outcomes confirm that valorisation-

based CE strategies can shift residual flows from waste management toward value creation.a

5.4 Sustainable Packaging and Material Substitution (Packaging Industry, Retailers, Consumers)

SILLs involved: SILL2

Material substitution represents a complementary CE strategy for reducing environmental burdens associated with packaging and improving food preservation. **SILL2** developed a biodegradable and compostable tray and lid that significantly reduced carbon footprint while maintaining functional performance. The extended shelf-life delivered by the packaging contributed to FLW prevention across retail and consumer stages.

The sustainability and economic assessments indicated that such biobased packaging solutions could become competitive in the market, supported by potential reductions in carbon-related costs and favourable cost-benefit ratios. These findings position the packaging industry as a key enabler in circular transition pathways, with material innovation serving both climate and resource efficiency objectives.e

5.5 Behavioural Change and Responsible Consumption (Consumers, Civil Society)

SILLs involved: SILL9, supported by SILL2

Consumers play a critical role in closing circular loops through food management practices and purchasing decisions. **SILL9** demonstrated how integrated labels, improved information on product quality, and leftover-based recipes can influence consumption behaviours and reduce FLW at household level. When combined with sustainable packaging (**SILL2**), these interventions generated strong reductions in waste generation and associated emissions during the testing phase.

These findings highlight the importance of aligning material innovation with behavioural guidance. Together, they show how CE strategies at the consumer level can reinforce upstream prevention efforts and support transitions toward circular, resource-efficient household practices.

5.6 System Transparency and Digital Enabling (Cross-Actor Support)

SILLs involved: SILL1

Enabling mechanisms form the digital backbone of circular food systems, supporting monitoring, forecasting, and decision-making across actors. **SILL1** developed a platform for aggregating accessible data from food system stakeholders, contributing to transparency and shared situational awareness.

Although the platform influences FLW only indirectly, it supports CE strategies by enhancing coordination and facilitating evidence-based planning.

The inclusion of this enabling layer reinforces the understanding that circularity relies not only on technological interventions but also on data governance, cross-actor visibility, and systemic integration.

6 Gender-based interpretation of results

This chapter provides an analysis based on the data provided by the SILLs regarding gender participation in the development and implementation of the respective SILL activities. The assessment was conducted in two complementary steps. A first qualitative analysis focused on **SILLs 2-9**, based on self-reported indicators covering gender balance, leadership, access to resources, communication practices, and integration of gender aspects in research activities. At a later stage, **gender-disaggregated quantitative participation data were also collected**, allowing the analysis to be extended to **all nine SILLs**, including **SILL 1**, and supporting a consolidated comparison of participation patterns, as illustrated in **Figure 9**.

Across the SILLs assessed in the first phase (SILL 2-9), gender balance and inclusiveness were systematically considered, with **generally positive but differentiated results**. **SILL 2, SILL 3, SILL 4, and SILL 5** demonstrated strong gender equality across teams, leadership, and operational activities. **SILL 4** stands out for achieving **maximum scores across all qualitative indicators** and for its progressive openness to non-binary classifications. **SILL 5** also achieved balanced employment and leadership structures, supported by strong gender-sensitive communication and data collection, while showing opportunities to further strengthen access to resources and gender-specific health benefits, particularly relevant in operational contexts where women are often represented.

SILL 6 and SILL 8 reported similarly balanced participation among staff and broadly equitable impacts across genders, supported by effective internal communication practices. At the same time, both SILLs identified room for improvement in the **systematic integration of gender aspects into research activities** and in outreach to gender-focused external organisations. **SILL 7**, while maintaining equality in daily operations and inclusive communication, experienced a decline in female participation following project restructuring, which was reflected in weaker performance in leadership balance, gender-disaggregated data collection, and external partnerships. **SILL 9** reported an overall balanced team composition, but with leadership roles predominantly held by men and more limited integration of gender considerations in research and monitoring practices.

To further illustrate these qualitative findings, Table 39 summarises the main strengths and remaining gaps identified across **SILLs 2-9** in relation to gender

balance and inclusiveness. The table highlights consistent achievements, such as gender-balanced teams, equal access to resources, and gender-sensitive communication, while also pointing to areas for further consolidation, notably in **gender-disaggregated data collection, integration of gender in research activities**, and the establishment of **balanced external partnerships**.

Table 39: Gender balance, strenghts and weaknesses

SILL	Main Strengths	Main Weaknesses / Gaps
SILL2	Full gender balance across staff, leadership, and operations. Equal access to resources (5/5) and strong gender-sensitive communication (5/5).	Gender-balanced partnerships (2/5) and data collection (3/5) remain limited; gender integration in research modest (3/5).
SILL3	Maintains full gender balance and equitable access to resources; gender-sensitive communication confirmed.	Gender-disaggregated data not collected; no explicit gender balance in partnerships or structured health benefits.
SILL4	Outstanding performance: 5/5 across all indicators, including leadership, research, and outreach. Integrates openness to non-binary inclusion.	None identified — represents best practice for gender mainstreaming.
SILL5	Full balance in employment and leadership; data collection (5/5) and gender-sensitive language strong.	Limited access to resources (3/5), gender-specific health benefits (1/5), and gender integration in research (1/5).
SILL6	Balanced partnerships and strong communication (5/5); data collection and equitable impact confirmed.	Leadership only partly balanced (3/5); moderate integration of gender in research and outreach (3/5).
SILL7	Equality in daily operations and inclusive communication (5/5); good access to resources (5/5).	Decline in female participation; lack of gender-disaggregated data (1/5), poor integration in research (1/5), and weak outreach (1/5).
SILL8	Gender balance achieved; equal access to resources (5/5); strong communication (5/5).	Gender integration in research (1/5), limited outreach (1/5), and unbalanced partnerships (3/5).
SILL9	Gender-balanced team overall (2 men, 3 women); equality in operations; good access to resources (5/5).	Men hold leadership roles; weak gender integration and data collection (1–3/5); partnerships not fully balanced.

Figure 9: SILLs Gender Distribution

The gender-disaggregated assessment across **all nine SILLs**, including **SILL 1**, demonstrates a **consistently balanced and inclusive participation framework**, with women representing a **slight majority of overall participants**, as shown in Figure 9. Full gender parity is observed in **SILL 3 and SILL 4**, both in overall participation and, where data are available, in leadership and coordination roles. A female-majority participation pattern is evident in **SILL 2, SILL 6, SILL 8, and SILL 9**, where women account for approximately **60–65%** of reported participants.

Importantly, female representation frequently extends beyond participation into **leadership and coordination roles**, particularly in **SILL 2 and SILL 6**, indicating that gender balance is reflected not only in team composition but also in decision-making structures. In SILLs where male participation is slightly higher, such as **SILL 1 and SILL 5**, women remain actively involved across key functional roles, including coordination and engagement, confirming a balanced distribution of responsibilities.

Overall, the combined qualitative and quantitative evidence confirms that **no SILL exhibits significant gender imbalance**, and that gender diversity is consistently present across technical, operational, and leadership roles. Observed variations are primarily linked to **organisational context, sectoral characteristics, and team size**, rather than structural barriers.

In conclusion, the SILL framework demonstrates a **robust and positive gender profile**, combining balanced participation, meaningful representation in leadership roles, and strong inclusion across career stages.

7 Lessons Learnt for the SILLs

The comparative analysis across all SILLs highlights that while each SILL addressed FLW reduction from different angles, several cross-cutting lessons emerged regarding data management, solution maturity, stakeholder coordination, and the interpretation of sustainability impact. The R3 evaluation also demonstrates that adaptive approaches, particularly those that combine quantitative data with contextual and qualitative insights, were essential to accurately assess the systemic performance of the SILLs. Across all SILLs, the lessons converge on several key points. Effective data management, transparency in communication, and methodological adaptability are indispensable for credible impact assessment. Projects that coupled quantitative analysis with qualitative understanding achieved the most consistent progress. Moreover, early validation of assumptions and stakeholder co-creation in interpreting results proved critical for ensuring that sustainability benefits are both measurable and meaningful. Together, these lessons reinforce the value of iterative, evidence-based learning for advancing systemic innovation in FLW reduction.

7.1 SILL 1 F2F FLW monitoring & assessment

For **SILL 1**, which focuses on the development of the FLW monitoring and assessment platform, the main lesson is that establishing robust and interoperable data infrastructure requires sustained investment in both technical capacity and stakeholder engagement. Although the platform itself does not directly reduce FLW, its value lies in enabling better decision-making through improved data accessibility and transparency. The experience underlines that ensuring long-term functionality and scalability of such tools depends on maintaining partnerships, regular data updates, and user-oriented design adjustments.

7.2 SILL 2 Innovative sustainable and smart packaging for fresh products

In SILL2, the development of smart, biodegradable packaging showed strong potential to enhance shelf life and reduce waste by integrating innovative materials and a freshness indicator. However, full deployment could not be completed within the project timeframe, demonstrating the need for adaptable validation strategies when real-world implementation is delayed. The experience also highlighted that collecting reliable impact estimations from stakeholders—both retailers and consumers—is challenging when the packaging prototype is not yet physically available: their assumptions are uncertain, and responses may be unintentionally biased by how questions are framed. For future initiatives, it is therefore recommended to provide at least validated sample tests or small pilot batches,

ensuring that stakeholders can interact with the packaging directly and generate more accurate, evidence-based estimations. Despite these constraints, combining qualitative insights with preliminary quantitative indications still proved valuable, and close collaboration with retailers and consumers remains essential to bridge the gap between laboratory advances and market-ready applications.

7.3 SILL 3 Wasteless greenhouse solutions for (pre)harvesting aligned with short-term downstream demand

SILL 3 confirmed that precision technologies in greenhouse management can effectively lower post-harvest losses, though initial results were below target expectations. The experience showed that continuous monitoring and iterative adaptation of data models are crucial for maintaining reliability. Periodic recalibration of baseline assumptions and improved coordination with growers are necessary to capture the true magnitude of the reduction potential. Flexibility and early integration of feedback loops proved decisive for sustaining progress toward long-term sustainability outcomes.

7.4 SILL 4: Mobile food valorisation as a service

The implementation of mobile food valorisation in SILL 4 showed the potential of converting surplus produce into value-added products, but also highlighted challenges in interpreting large datasets from processing trials. The experience demonstrated that clear system boundaries, well-defined assumptions, and structured scenarios are just as important as the data itself. When assessing small-scale, non-industrial operations, methodologies must be adapted to real conditions—such as variable feedstock, batch sizes, labour inputs, and the involvement of social-economy partners—to avoid misrepresenting impacts. Close collaboration between the pilot and evaluation teams proved essential to ensure that the analysis accurately reflected how local hubs operate and to produce meaningful, actionable insights.

7.5 SILL 5 Ugly food early identification, shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation

In SILL5, which integrates NG Sensor and Multiscan technologies to recover and valorise previously rejected tomatoes, the assessment demonstrated that food loss and waste reduction was substantial. However, it also became clear that careful interpretation of the GHG results was essential. The initial energy consumption values—derived from non-optimised or larger-scale production settings—had a disproportionately high influence on the calculated emissions. To avoid misleading

conclusions, it was necessary to adapt and scale these values to the actual operational context of the implemented solution. This experience highlights that technological gains in FLW reduction must always be evaluated together with their environmental implications, and that early energy-efficiency assessments, along with rigorous cross-checking of operational datasets, are crucial to ensure reliable and credible sustainability claims.

7.6 SILL6 : FLW reduction through advanced data-driven production process control & optimisation

In SILL6, the solution was structured around three applications designed to detect and prevent quality deviations in poultry meat processing. Two of the applications were successfully validated, while the third could not be fully implemented within the project timeframe. Despite this partial deployment, the overall results showed meaningful reductions in food loss and waste, accompanied by corresponding improvements in GHG-related emissions. A key lesson learned is that close and continuous collaboration with the SILL partners was essential to obtain accurate operational data and realistic estimations, ensuring that the environmental benefits reflected the actual performance of the technologies. This experience reinforces the value of early engagement with industrial stakeholders to secure reliable inputs and strengthen the credibility of impact assessments..

7.7 SILL 7: FLW reduction through efficient food bank networks

The experience of **SILL 7** stands out for its effective data provision and clarity, which enabled a seamless evaluation process. The lesson learned here is that investing in comprehensive and well-structured datasets from the beginning greatly improves analytical precision and reduces delays. Moreover, this SILL demonstrated that increased donations to food banks not only reduce retail FW but also contribute directly to food security objectives, reinforcing the systemic social value of redistribution mechanisms.

7.8 SILL 8 Retail FLW valorisation through algae production for high-value applications

In **SILL 8**, which focuses on retail-level valorisation of FW into microalgae feed, data were well-prepared but interpretation challenges emerged due to ambiguous template use. The lesson learned is that structured communication between SILL teams and evaluators, through clarifying exchanges and mutual validation steps, is essential for avoiding misalignment. This also underscores the importance of documenting assumptions in innovative value chains where processes and outputs differ from conventional food pathways. For example, in SILL 8, the production of

microalgae feed from food waste represents a novel process for which LCSA studies are largely undocumented.

7.9 SILL 9: “Fork to Farm to Fork “ (3F): Informing and nudging consumers to make better choices through reverse (dietetics) and forward (FLW, sustainability, affordability) optimisation

SILL9 provided a clear example of the limitations of relying solely on consumer self-reporting to measure FLW reduction. Although the modelling offered useful insights, empirical validation remained constrained. Some real-world evidence was collected, but it was based on a very small sample and a short observation period, making the results highly sensitive to individual consumer behaviour. This underscores that consumer-driven solutions require robust in-home testing and behavioural monitoring to generate reliable evidence. The key lesson learned is the need to bridge the gap between theoretical models and actual user practices, ensuring that real-world consumer insights are systematically incorporated into both the design and evaluation of FLW-reduction strategies.

8 Conclusions

The findings of R3 offer a consolidated and more mature understanding of how the ZeroW SILL innovation perform across environmental, economic, and social sustainability dimensions. Compared with earlier rounds, the final datasets benefits from more complete implementation experiences, clarified SB, revised assumptions, and improved data validation directly from SILL partners. This increases the robustness of the assessment and allows the results to be interpreted in a broader systemic context, beyond individual SILL.

Across the SILL portfolio, the results demonstrate that meaningful reductions in FLW are achievable when technological innovation are combined with organisational adaptation, business models, regulatory compliance and behavioural change. At the same time, the R3 assessment make clear that the pathway to sustainability varies significantly across value chain stages, requiring tailored approaches and continuous learning.

From an environmental sustainability perspective, the majority of SILLs achieved notable reduction in FLW-related GHG emissions. Solutions focused on optimisation, advanced sorting and mobile valorisation generated proportionate decreases in GHG emissions by diverting substantial quantities of food away from waste streams. Retail and consumer-facing solutions demonstrated that even modest operational adjustments or behavioural nudges can result in considerable climate benefits. In minority of cases, environmental gains were partially offset by increased energy use, highlighting the need for improved operational efficiency and optimised energy sourcing as solutions scale.

The economic interpretation confirms that ZeroW innovation generally produce positive financial outcomes, either through avoided losses, improved product quality, or enhanced value recovery. In nearly all cases, CBR exceed one, demonstrating that the economic benefits outweigh associated costs over the operational period assessed. Redistribution systems produced exceptionally high returns per euro invested, while valorisation-based solutions showed strong potential contingent on future optimisation of resource use. All SILLs had indicate that the distribution of costs and benefits remains fair and does not create disproportionate burdens for specific stakeholder groups.

From a social and health perspective, the results demonstrate meaningful contributions to food security, consumer empowerment, and stakeholder engagement. Solutions aimed at redistribution increased food availability for vulnerable groups, while behavioural and information-based solutions strengthened stakeholder capacity to reduce FLW and make healthier, more sustainable choices. S-LCA results across multiple SILLs reveal stability in governance, supplier relationships, and workplace conditions, although limitations remain in areas such as gender-sensitive monitoring, community impact evaluation, and user feedback systems. These gaps indicate the need for long-term engagement to achieve deeper

social change, particularly where societal habits and perceptions of FLW are concerned.

A cross-cutting finding from R3 is the importance of data clarity, methodological consistency, and continued dialogue between SILLs and the assessment team. Several SILLs required substantial clarification to align datasets with real-world conditions, and where implementation was partial, qualitative or model-based estimations were applied. Conversely, some SILLs demonstrated the benefits of comprehensive and well-prepared datasets, which facilitated a smooth evaluation process and strengthened confidence in the results. These differences underline the value of adopting common data standards, explicit assumptions, and iterative refinements throughout the project cycle.

Overall, the results illustrate that technological innovation alone does not guarantee sustainability impact, rather, a combination of behavioural incentives, business model adjustments, operational optimisation, and stakeholder coordination is required. The R3 insights confirm that each SILL contributed distinctively to the overarching ZeroW objectives, regardless of implementation maturity. Some achieved direct and quantifiable impact, other advanced the methodological and organisational groundwork needed for future scaling, and several demonstrated the feasibility of systemic approaches that integrate environmental, economic, and social considerations.

Taken together, the R3 results show that the ZeroW SILL portfolio has developed a strong foundation for broader replication and scale-up. While further validation and real-world testing will be required for some solutions, the evidence base generated through final assessment provides clear guidance for policy, industry, and community actors. It demonstrates that systemic FLW reduction is achievable through coordinated innovation efforts, and that such efforts can simultaneously generate environmental, economic, and social benefits, supporting the transition to a more circular, resilient, and equitable European food system.

9 References

Cecilia Casonato, L. G.-H. (2023). What a waste! Evidence of consumer food waste prevention and its effectiveness.

Felicitas Schneider, M. E. (2020). Food Waste (And Loss) at the Retail Level.

Kumar, D. &. (2017). Reducing Postharvest Losses during Storage of Grain Crops to Strengthen Food Security in Developing Countries.

(2024). *SILL Strategic Plan*.

10 Annex

10.1 Actor-based interpretation of results

In this chapter the assessment of the innovations is analysed through the perspective of the food supply chain actors, as well as the ones that are contributing to the reduction of the FLW through the innovations, such as foodbanks, packing industry, alternative protein producers, etc. stakeholders as identified by the SILLs.

10.1.1 Producers and post-harvest operations

Producers and post-harvest operation within ZeroW were primarily addressed through the activities of **SILL 3, SILL 4, and SILL 5**, each targeted the improvement of efficiency, quality assurance, and valorisation practices along the agri-food chain. **SILL 3** focused on primary production, applying advanced remote sensing technologies for crop monitoring, yield estimation, and harvest planning. These tools helped producers better align harvest timing and volumes with available storage and downstream handling capacity, reducing avoidable waste already at farm level. In the immediate post-harvest stage, **SILL 4** implemented valorisation pathways for downgraded or surplus fruits and vegetables (streams that typically arise at, or immediately after, harvest). By converting these into stable food products and ingredients, SILL 4 demonstrated practical ways to extend shelf life and reduce the volume of produce otherwise discarded or down-graded. **SILL 5** addressed the early step of post-harvest quality management, introducing non-destructive multi-sensor platforms for real-time quality assessment of fresh produce before it enters the market. These tools improved classification accuracy, reduced unnecessary rejection, and supported better decision-making for the next steps in the value chain.

Taken together, the innovations across SILL 3-5 delivered measurable benefits for food producers and post-harvest operators, enhancing operational performance, environmental sustainability, and resilience across the value chain. The combined implementation of these solutions led to an **average reduction FLW of approximately 45%**, mainly due to more precise harvest planning, improved post-harvest process control, and enhanced valorisation of downgraded streams. The associated **reduction in GHG emissions reached around 63%**, reflecting improved resource efficiency. The **overall resilience capacity** of producers was also increased, with composite evaluations indicating an **average score above 4.5/5**, confirming enhanced adaptive management and operational stability. Overall, these results demonstrate that the integrated deployment of ZeroW solutions in primary production and post-harvest operation (across **SILL 3, SILL 4, and SILL 5**) provides a coherent and effective framework for reducing FLW, improving quality, and

supporting a transition toward more sustainable and circular food production systems.

10.1.2 Processors

From the perspective of food processors, the results obtained from **SILL 4 and SILL 6** demonstrate notable progress in improving efficiency, product recovery, and environmental performance across two distinct processing contexts. These SILLs collectively illustrate how tailored technological interventions can reduce FLW while strengthening process control and resource efficiency. **SILL 4** focused on fruit and vegetable valorisation, converting downgraded and surplus produce into shelf-stable products and ingredients, thereby extending the usability of raw materials and mitigating losses that would otherwise occur both before and after harvest. **SILL 6**, operating within the poultry meat industry, developed portable NIR sensors and chemometric models to support real-time quality control and salt content optimisation during processing. Despite operating in different sectors, both pilots showed comparable gains in process precision and material recovery, contributing to substantial reductions in FLW and associated GHG emissions during the testing phase. Improvements in product conformity further highlighted the effectiveness of data-driven quality management within these environments. Resilience capacity assessments indicated that processors benefitted from enhanced adaptability and operational continuity, even when operating under variable conditions. Overall, these results demonstrate that the ZeroW processing solutions—whether focused on valorisation or digital quality optimisation—can jointly deliver meaningful environmental and operational benefits for food processors.

10.1.3 Retailers

From the perspective of food retailers, the combined outcomes of **SILL 2, SILL 5, SILL 7, and SILL 8** demonstrate how a diverse set of technological and organisational solutions can collectively mitigate FLW while strengthening sustainability across the retail value chain. These SILLs address different stages of retail operations—from packaging and quality assurance to redistribution and valorisation—yet converge toward the same objective of reducing waste generation and improving resource efficiency. In **SILL 2**, the focus on sustainability was particularly evident through the substitution of fossil-based plastics with **biodegradable and compostable materials**, confirmed by an **average 45% reduction in carbon footprint** compared to conventional trays and lids. This environmental gain, combined with an approximate **20% extension in product shelf life**, demonstrates the dual contribution of sustainable packaging to both climate impact reduction and food preservation. **SILL 5** complemented these advances through enhanced pre-sorting of fresh produce, ensuring that only high-quality products reach the retail phase, thereby extending shelf-life potential and

limiting in-store losses. In parallel, **SILL 7** supported redistribution practices by developing digital tools that improve coordination between donors and food banks, transforming surplus stock into socially beneficial resources. **SILL 8** addressed the management of unavoidable waste through innovative pre-treatment and valorisation, converting fruit, vegetable, and protein residues into feedstock for microalgae production within a safe and traceable reverse-logistics framework.

Collectively, these diverse yet complementary solutions achieved an **average 35% reduction in FLW** and a **64% decrease in associated GHG emissions** at the retailer level, confirming the strong environmental and operational impact of integrated prevention, redistribution, and valorisation measures. The **complete elimination of fossil-based packaging materials** within SILL 2 further underscores the shift toward circularity, while the cluster's **resilience capacity** (average score of **4.1/5**) highlights the strengthened ability of retailers to adapt to supply variability and sustainability challenges. Overall, the SILLs demonstrate that combining **sustainable packaging, precision sorting, efficient redistribution, and bio-based valorisation** offers a comprehensive strategy to advance circular, low-impact, and resilient retail food systems.

10.1.4 Consumers

From the consumer perspective, the combined outcomes of **SILL 2** and **SILL 9** demonstrate how sustainable packaging solutions and behaviour-oriented interventions can jointly reduce FLW while fostering more responsible consumption patterns. **SILL 2** contributed to this objective through the introduction of **biodegradable and compostable food packaging** that prolongs product shelf life by approximately **20%**, helping consumers preserve food quality and reduce premature disposal. **SILL 9**, in parallel, addressed behavioural drivers of waste generation by promoting awareness of proper food preservation and the correct interpretation of “best before” dates. The introduction of **integrated food labels**—combining nutritional value, GHG emissions, and FLW information—encourages consumers to make more informed and sustainable food choices. Furthermore, the development of **weekly recipes designed to reuse leftovers** has proven effective in reducing household waste while maintaining nutritional balance and dietary quality.

At the consumer cluster level, these complementary solutions resulted in an **average 52% reduction in FLW** and a corresponding **52% decrease in GHG emissions** associated with FLW, demonstrating strong environmental and behavioural impact. In addition, the **complete elimination of fossil-based packaging materials** achieved through SILL 2 reinforces the shift toward circular consumption and more sustainable household practices. The **resilience capacity**, averaging **4/5**, indicates enhanced consumer adaptability and awareness in

managing food resources. Overall, the consumer cluster's performance confirms that combining **sustainable packaging with behaviourally informed interventions** can effectively mitigate FLW, lower environmental burdens, and promote lasting transitions toward circular and resource-efficient food systems.

10.1.5 Packaging industry

From the perspective of the packaging industry, the outcomes of **SILL 2** demonstrate the strong environmental and economic potential of transitioning toward **biodegradable, compostable, and bio-based packaging materials**. The newly developed tray and lid achieved a substantial reduction in carbon footprint compared to conventional fossil-based alternatives, confirming that sustainable materials can meet functional performance requirements while significantly lowering climate impacts. This reduced carbon intensity also enhances the **market competitiveness** of the solution, as lower lifecycle emissions can translate into **reduced costs associated with carbon taxation** and improved alignment with emerging regulatory frameworks on packaging sustainability. Beyond its environmental advantages, the packaging extended product shelf life by approximately **20%**, contributing to reduced FLW and improved preservation across retail and consumer stages. The **CBA** further supports its feasibility, indicating a **CBR of 1.94**, suggesting that the solution can be **economically viable and attractive for market adoption**. Overall, the SILL 2 results highlight that the packaging industry can act as a pivotal driver of circular transformation—delivering both **climate and economic benefits** through low-impact material innovation, while enhancing efficiency and sustainability across the food value chain.

10.1.6 Foodbanks

From the perspective of food banks, the results of **SILL 7** highlight the strong potential of redistribution as a cost-effective and environmentally beneficial strategy to reduce FLW. Through the development of predictive tools for matching supply and demand, decision-support systems for donation management, and guidelines for best practices, SILL 7 has enhanced the coordination between donor companies and food banks, improving both efficiency and the volume of food recovered. The **CBA** confirms the high overall return of this approach, with redistribution delivering significant combined economic and environmental benefits compared to the associated operational costs. The analysis also underscores the contribution of all food categories—particularly cereals—in ensuring consistent positive outcomes. Beyond its financial effectiveness, the redistribution model developed under SILL 7 contributes to reducing GHG emissions and diverting edible food from waste streams to human consumption. Overall, these results demonstrate that structured

food donation systems can act as a key mechanism for advancing social responsibility, environmental sustainability, and circularity within the food system

10.1.7 Food valorisation

From a **food valorisation** perspective, the combined outcomes of **SILL 4** and **SILL 8** clearly demonstrate the potential of converting surplus, downgraded, or unavoidable food materials into new value streams that contribute to both waste reduction and resource efficiency. The integrated valorisation strategies tested across the two pilots enabled the recovery of nutrients and functional compounds from fruits, vegetables, and animal-based products that would otherwise be discarded. These materials were successfully reintroduced into the food and feed chains through stable, marketable products and bio-based applications, illustrating a shift from waste management to value creation. The results confirm that valorisation represents a critical lever for decoupling food production from its environmental burden: by transforming side streams into new raw materials, overall FLW were significantly reduced, and associated GHG emissions decreased correspondingly. Beyond environmental gains, these approaches also strengthen supply chain resilience by diversifying product portfolios and stabilising returns from variable raw material inputs. Overall, the experiences from SILL 4 and SILL 8 underline that valorisation-based interventions can effectively operationalise circular economy principles in the food sector, transforming residual flows into economically and environmentally valuable resources.

